

Integrating Field Ecology and Sentinel-2-Compatible Remote Sensing for Monitoring Vegetation Succession in Natura 2000 Dry Grasslands

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doi: 10.5281/zenodo.20407625

Abstract: Dry continental grasslands (Natura 2000 habitat type 6210 – *Festuco-Brometalia*) are increasingly threatened by land abandonment and vegetation succession (Management Plan for the Natura 2000 Sites Potok Dolje and Vejalnica and Krč and the Goranec Significant Landscape, 2023). This paper presents initial results of an ongoing remote sensing study aimed at developing a satellite-based framework for monitoring succession in these habitats, using Natura 2000 site Vejalnica and Krč (HR2001298) and the Goranec Significant Landscape (City of Zagreb, Croatia) as calibration and validation sites. Field surveys and unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV) mapping were conducted in 2024–2025 across approximately 150 ha of (semi-)grassland areas. A modified EMBAL field protocol was applied for habitat delineation and ground-truth. UAV Red, Green, Blue (RGB) and multispectral imagery were processed to derive a canopy height model, from which four structural succession phases were defined. The study area was aligned to a 10 × 10 m grid compatible with Sentinel-2 pixels. Baseline mapping revealed strong spatial heterogeneity and widespread shrub and tree encroachment, providing a basis for modelling Sentinel-2 spectral metrics for monitoring succession phases in grassland habitats.

Keywords: UAV; multispectral imagery; habitat 6210; NDVI; mapping; shrub encroachment.

1 Introduction

Dry continental grasslands of Natura 2000 habitat type 6210 (*Festuco-Brometalia*) are increasingly threatened by land abandonment and subsequent vegetation succession, resulting in shrub and tree encroachment and gradual habitat loss. Their monitoring is important for conservation management, but field-based assessment alone is difficult to apply consistently over larger areas, while satellite observations require ecologically meaningful calibration. This paper presents initial results of a broader remote sensing study aimed at developing a satellite-based framework for monitoring succession in dry grasslands. The present phase focuses on integrating field survey and UAV-derived structural mapping with a Sentinel-2-compatible 10 × 10 m spatial framework to generate a reference dataset for subsequent modelling. In the next phase of the research, multi-year Sentinel-2 NDVI and related spectral metrics will be analysed as predictors of structurally defined succession stages.

2 Materials and methods

The study was conducted at Natura 2000 site HR2001298 Vejalnica and Krč, located in the southeastern foothills of Mt. Medvednica (45°54'00.0"N, 16°04'58.8"E), Croatia, at approximately 400 m a.s.l. More than half of the site overlaps with the Goranec Significant Landscape. The analysed grassland areas comprise two spatially separated units: Vejalnica (approximately 37 ha) and Krč (approximately 106 ha), together representing the main target area for habitat 6210 assessment.

2.1 Field survey and UAV data acquisition

Field surveys were conducted in 2024–2025 to support habitat delineation, validation of structural classes, and interpretation of succession patterns. Data collection was based on a modified EMBAL protocol, where EMBAL refers to the “European Monitoring of Biodiversity in Agricultural Landscapes” field methodology developed for standardized biodiversity and habitat surveys in agricultural landscapes (European Environment Agency 2021). In this study, the protocol was adapted to the ecological and management context of habitat 6210 and implemented through standardized field forms for grassland and succession assessment.

UAV surveys were carried out in October 2024. RGB imagery was acquired using a DJI Matrice 350 RTK equipped with a Zenmuse P1 camera, while multispectral imagery was collected using DJI P4 Multispectral and eBeeSQ platforms. Flights were conducted at 120 m above ground level with 70–85% image overlap. Multispectral acquisition covered 136 ha in total, including 47 ha at Vejalnica and 89 ha at Krč, producing RGB and multispectral imagery with spatial resolutions of approximately 9 cm and 15 cm, respectively.

2.2 Data processing and structural classification

The acquired UAV imagery was processed into orthomosaics and elevation products for subsequent structural analysis. RGB orthophotos were generated in Agisoft Metashape Professional, while multispectral products were further used to derive orthomosaics, DSM/DTM surfaces, and vegetation indices. A vegetation canopy height layer was then derived from the surface and terrain models and classified into four structural succession phases: F0, open grassland, F1, shrubs below 1 m, F2, shrubs 1–4 m, and F3, trees above 4 m. These

structural classes represent a simplified succession gradient from open grassland to woody vegetation.

2.3 Sentinel-2 spatial harmonization

To ensure direct interoperability with Sentinel-2 data, the study area was divided into a 10 × 10 m grid fully aligned with Sentinel-2 pixels in WGS84 / UTM Zone 33N (Figure 5). For each grid cell, zonal statistics were calculated to quantify the proportional cover of succession phases F0–F3. This grid-level structural dataset represented the calibration layer for the broader research framework, in which multi-year Sentinel-2 NDVI metrics were tested as predictors of succession intensity and stage.

Figure 5. 10 × 10 m grid over Vejalnica area, fully aligned with Sentinel-2 pixels in WGS84 / UTM Zone 33N.

3 Results

The results represent the baseline structural dataset used to support the development of a satellite-based framework for monitoring grassland succession. The two study sites revealed a clear predominance of woody vegetation and only fragmented remnants of open grassland. These structural patterns provide a baseline for linking UAV-derived succession phases with Sentinel-2 spectral metrics and for subsequent model calibration. At Vejalnica, forests and shrub mosaics occupied nearly half of the mapped area, while shrub-dominated classes accounted for approximately one third (Table 3). Grassland and grassland mosaics covered about 10.2 ha, corresponding to roughly 28% of the site. At Krč, the structural pattern was even more shifted towards advanced succession: forests and mosaics covered almost 50% of the area, shrub-related classes

about 27%, and grassland or grassland mosaics approximately 17 ha, or about 16% of the site. These results indicate that both sites are characterized by extensive woody encroachment and fragmented persistence of open habitat, with Krč showing a more advanced structural transition toward shrub and tree dominance.

3.1 Grid-based structural succession patterns

The 10 × 10 m harmonized grid preserved fine-scale structural variability while ensuring direct compatibility with Sentinel-2 pixels. At Vejalnica, grid cells with higher grassland proportion formed a discontinuous mosaic embedded within a matrix of shrub and tree cover (Figure 6). Intermediate succession phases were widespread, while tree-dominated cells were concentrated in larger continuous patches. At Krč, the grid revealed a stronger concentration of advanced succession, with broad areas occupied by woody vegetation and fewer persistent open-grassland cells (Figure 7). The spatial structure therefore indicates a clear difference between the two sites: Vejalnica retains more dispersed open patches, whereas Krč is characterized by stronger structural closure and reduced openness at the 10 m scale.

Figure 6. Proportion of the grassland in the Vejalnica area. The share was calculated as the percentage cover of vegetation within a 10 × 10 m grid (base map: Topographic Map of the Republic of Croatia, source: Geoportal.hr, processed by Oikon d.o.o., 2025).

Table 3. Structural characteristics of the two study sites derived from habitat mapping and UAV-supported analysis.

Site	Total mapped area (ha)	Grassland and grassland mosaics (ha)	Grassland (%)	Forest and forest-shrub mosaics (%)	Main structural pattern
Vejalnica	36.97	10.2	28	~49	Fragmented open grassland embedded in shrub and forest matrix
Krč	105.77	~17.0	16	~50	Strong woody dominance and advanced succession with limited open patches

Figure 7. Proportion of the grassland in the Krč area. The share was calculated as the percentage cover of vegetation within a 10×10 m grid (base map: Topographic Map of the Republic of Croatia, source: Geoportal.hr, processed by Oikon d.o.o., 2025).

4 Discussion

The results indicate extensive shrub and tree encroachment at both study sites, with open grassland occurring mainly as fragmented patches. This finding supports the main aim of the study, which was to establish a structural reference dataset for monitoring succession in Natura 2000 dry grasslands using remote sensing. The dominance of woody vegetation suggests that vegetation succession following land abandonment is currently the primary driver of habitat change in the study area.

Similar patterns have been widely documented in semi-natural grasslands across Europe, where the cessation of traditional land management leads to shrub expansion and gradual transition toward forest vegetation. Our findings are also consistent with previous analyses conducted in the Vejalnica–Krč area, which reported a long-term decline of open grassland surfaces and increasing forest cover (Vitasović Kosić et al. 2011).

From a methodological perspective, the integration of field surveys, UAV mapping and a Sentinel-2-compatible spatial grid represent a key strength of the study. UAV-derived structural data provide detailed information on vegetation height and composition, while satellite observations enable scalable monitoring across larger areas. In this context, the structural patterns presented here should not be interpreted solely as a site-specific assessment, but as a calibration dataset for developing transferable satellite-based monitoring approaches. Similar studies have shown that Sentinel-2 imagery can successfully estimate grassland vegetation parameters such as biomass, vegetation density and canopy structure, supporting its use in large-scale grassland monitoring (Schwieder et al. 2020).

However, some limitations should be considered. Small grassland fragments may fall below the effective spatial resolution of Sentinel-2 pixels, potentially introducing classification uncertainty. Future research will therefore focus on testing NDVI-based models for predicting

succession intensity and monitoring habitat dynamics over time.

5 Conclusions

This study provides initial results of a broader research framework aimed at monitoring succession in Natura 2000 dry grasslands using remote sensing. The analysis revealed extensive shrub and tree encroachment at both study sites, with open grasslands persisting mainly as fragmented patches. These findings confirm that vegetation succession driven by land abandonment is a major driver of habitat change in the study area. By integrating field surveys, UAV-derived structural mapping and a Sentinel-2-compatible spatial grid, the study establishes a reference dataset for future satellite-based monitoring. This dataset will be used in the next phase of the research to test whether multi-temporal Sentinel-2 NDVI metrics can predict succession phases. The proposed approach demonstrates the potential of combining high-resolution UAV data with satellite observations for scalable monitoring of grassland ecosystems. Such methods may support long-term monitoring and conservation management of habitat type 6210 and other semi-natural grasslands.

6 References

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